

ON-LINE CONSOLIDATION MECHANISMS IN THERMOPLASTIC FILAMENT WINDING (TAPE LAYING)

C. E. CARPENTER and J. S. COLTON

Composites Manufacturing Research Program
The George W. Woodruff School of Mechanical Engineering
Georgia Institute of Technology
Atlanta, Georgia 30332 - 0405

ABSTRACT

The on-line consolidation process, using a single roller, in thermoplastic filament winding (tape laying) is investigated. A one-dimensional, semi-empirical, on-line consolidation process model is proposed that describes the deformation and flow phenomena. Composite rings are fabricated from 50 layers of 12K tow APC-2 tape (6 mm wide) on a 178 mm diameter mandrel. It was found that the winding speed had statistically significant effects on the void content, the fiber volume fraction, and the final thickness; whereas the applied load had a statistically significant effect on the final thickness.

KEYWORDS: tape laying, filament winding, consolidation modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic filament winding (tape laying) is a continuous process in which a thermoplastic composite material (usually in the form of a tape) is wound onto a mandrel and consolidated on-line, thus building up the desired shape in a layer-by-layer fashion. The continuous processing of thermoplastic composites with on-line consolidation can lead to potential cost savings in manufacturing because no secondary processing is needed to complete the consolidation process. Consolidation is a processing step in which heat and pressure are applied to the thermoplastic composite in order to eliminate spatial gaps and force out any entrapped air, thereby compressing and bonding the composite laminate into a void-free, finished part. Improper consolidation can lead to voids, residual stresses, warpage, and in some cases, premature mechanical failure of the composite part. There are several critical functions of the consolidation process that must be achieved in order to obtain a quality composite laminate with optimum properties [1]. These include complete bonding between the plies (or layers) of the composite laminate, prevention and removal of voids, attaining the desired fiber volume content in the part, attaining a uniform distribution of fibers and matrix within the part, attaining the desired dimensions of the part, and prevention of material degradation during the process.

The consolidation process can be divided into three mechanisms [2,3]: bulk consolidation, matrix flow, and fiber network deformation. Bulk consolidation eliminates the gaps between the composite layers and develops intimate contact. Matrix flow within each composite layer transports voids away from the interface and fills in matrix-depleted regions. The majority of the load applied to deform and compact the laminate is borne by the matrix during the first two stages of the consolidation process.

Elastic deformation of the fiber network occurs when the deformation is such that the matrix pressure rapidly decreases due to excess matrix flow. If this occurs, the elastic fiber network can be compressed to the point where it starts to take up a significant portion of the applied load. In this paper, only the deformation and flow will be discussed. The next section describes the model. The third section presents the experiments and the fourth a discussion of the results. The final section presents the conclusions.

2. DEFORMATION MODEL

The formulation of the deformation model for thermoplastic filament winding with on-line consolidation is presented and discussed in this section [4,5,6,7,8]. The model assumes that the primary deformation mechanisms are matrix flow parallel to the fibers and fiber bed compaction. These two mechanisms are assumed to occur as the towpreg passes through the nip region (the nip is the region of contact between the compaction roller and the incoming towpreg) (*Figure 1*).

2.1 Nip Length The contact length between the compaction roller and the towpreg being laid down, the nip length L , is obtained from the radius of the compaction roller and the reduction in towpreg thickness and can be written as

$$L = \sqrt{(t_0 - t_L)[2R - (t_0 - t_L)]} \quad (1)$$

where t_0 and t_L refer to the initial and final towpreg thicknesses, respectively, and R refers to the radius of the compaction roller.

2.2 Fiber Volume Fraction Distribution Applying fiber continuity and assuming the towpreg is transversely isotropic, the fiber volume fraction at a position, x , in the nip, $V_f(x)$, can be written in terms of the nip length as

$$V_f(x) = \frac{t_L V_L}{t_L + R - \sqrt{R^2 - (x - L)^2}} \quad (2)$$

where V_L refers to the fiber volume fraction of the consolidated towpreg.

2.3 Matrix Pressure Distribution As the towpreg passes through the nip region, large matrix pressure gradients are established along the length of the nip and across the width of the towpreg due to compaction by the roller. These gradients are essential for the formation of intimate contact and for the removal of voids because they induce matrix flow that fills in gaps and transports entrapped air out of the nip. Both longitudinal (parallel to the fibers) and transverse (perpendicular to the fibers) matrix flows are possible within the nip because pressure gradients exist in both directions. The matrix pressure gradient along the length of the nip, $\Delta p_m/L$, can be related to the matrix flow rate, $q(x)$, using D'Arcy's law modified by the Kozeny-Carman expression for permeability and by the Carreau model for shear-thinning fluids (*Equation 3*) [7]

$$\frac{\Delta p_m}{L} = \frac{4K\eta_a q(x)}{r_f^2} \frac{V_f(x)^2}{[1 - V_f(x)]^3} \quad (3)$$

with
$$q(x) = \left(\frac{1 - V_L}{V_L}\right) UV_f(x) \quad (4)$$

and
$$\eta_a = \eta_0(1 + (\lambda\dot{\gamma})^2)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

where r_f refers to the radius of the fibers and U to the winding speed. The symbol, η_0 , refers to the zero-shear-rate viscosity and the time constant, λ , refers to the shear rate at which shear-thinning effects become important. Both η_0 and λ depend on the process temperature. The power-law index, n , refers to the degree of shear thinning. These three viscosity model constants can be determined

from viscosity data obtained from simple flow experiments. The term $\dot{\gamma}$ refers to the average shear rate and is obtained from Newton's friction law for average conditions at the walls of a flow capillary [7]. The term K refers to the Kozeny constant, which is an indicator of the permeability of the fiber bed and is determined empirically. For the proposed one-dimensional deformation model, the Kozeny constant associated with flow parallel to the fiber direction will be used. The matrix pressure distribution, $p_m(x)$, is obtained by integrating *Equation 3* with respect to position in the nip.

2.4 Fiber Bed Pressure Distribution The fiber bed pressure distribution is obtained from Gutowski [9] and can be written as

$$p_f(x) = \frac{C \sqrt{\frac{V_f(x)}{V_0}} - 1}{\left(\sqrt{\frac{V_\infty}{V_f(x)}} - 1 \right)^4} \quad (6)$$

where C is a spring constant for the fiber bed and V_∞ is the highest fiber volume fraction obtainable. The term V_0 refers to the initial (or undeformed) fiber volume fraction of the towpreg. The value of V_0 cannot be obtained directly from the reported weight fractions and densities of the constituent materials because internal voids and surface irregularities exist in the towpreg material. Therefore, *Equation 2* was used to obtain an estimate for V_0 based upon the fiber volume fraction of the deformed towpreg and the initial and final towpreg thicknesses.

2.5 Predicted Applied Load The applied load necessary to achieve a given final laminate thickness or final fiber volume fraction can be obtained by integrating both the matrix and fiber pressure distributions over the length of the nip and multiplying this by the width of the towpreg. This can be expressed as

$$P_{\text{appl}} = w \int_0^L [p_m(x) + p_f(x)] dx \quad (7)$$

where P_{appl} refers to the predicted applied load and w refers to the width of the towpreg. *Equation 7* will be solved numerically and discussed below.

3. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

An experimental on-line consolidation mechanism was constructed and installed on a two-axis filament winding machine. It consisted of hot air guns that applied the required process heat and a pneumatically-controlled compaction roller that applied the required consolidation pressure. A 4,000 watt hot air gun was used to heat the incoming towpreg and a 2,000 watt hot air gun was used to heat the surface of the substrate (preprocessed layers) directly beneath the nip. Composite rings were fabricated at a process temperature of 400°C, winding speeds of 12.7, 31.8, and 50.8 mm/sec, and applied loads of 89, 156, and 222 N. The rings were wound from 50 layers of 6 mm wide APC-2 AS4 12K towpreg tape on a mandrel with a diameter of 178 mm. The towpreg had a manufacturer's reported fiber content of 62.1 percent by weight and an initial, average measured thickness of 0.237 mm. The thicknesses of the final samples were measured. The fiber volume content of each ring was determined using optical microscopy techniques. The void content of each ring was obtained using a density technique similar to that outlined in Method A of ASTM D2734.

A 2² factorial design with analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the effects of winding speed and applied load on the void content, fiber content, and final thickness of the consolidated specimens. For this investigation, the process temperatures were held constant and the winding speed and applied load were varied. A total of five experimental sets were performed (*Table 1*). The first four sets constituted the 2² factorial design. The last set corresponds to a verification set and was not used in the statistical analysis. Three rings were fabricated at each of the five experimental points for a total of 15 rings.

Table 1: Experimental Design

Experiment (i=1,2,3)	Winding Speed		Applied Load	
	(mm/sec)	(in/sec)	(N)	(lbf)
RS1-i	12.7	0.5	89	20
RS2-i	12.7	0.5	222	50
RS3-i	50.8	2.0	222	50
RS4-i	50.8	2.0	89	20
RS5-i	31.8	1.25	156	35

4. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

4.1 Empirical Determination of Model Parameters The predicted values for each of the empirically determined model parameters (the thickness of the deformed towpreg, the Kozeny constant, and the void content) were determined experimentally. It should be noted that the correlation equations obtained from the regression analyses are only applicable to the material, process, and equipment studied.

The relationship between the thickness and the fiber volume fraction of the deformed towpreg was determined from the experimental data as

$$t_L = 0.408 - 0.477 V_L \quad (\text{mm}) \quad (8)$$

where t_L refers to the deformed towpreg thickness expressed in millimeters and V_L refers to the fiber volume fraction of the deformed towpreg (consolidated). Equation 8 has a coefficient of determination (or "R²") of 0.983. This value of R² is close enough to unity to allow one to conclude that a linear relationship between the thickness and the fiber volume fraction of the deformed towpreg exists. This result represents the flattening out of surface features [10] and the elimination of voids, hence its linearity.

It is presumed that, for the experiments conducted, the Kozeny constant depends only upon the final fiber volume fraction, the winding speed (shear rate), and the nip length (flow path length). The remaining factors affecting the Kozeny constant are assumed to remain constant between the experiments. The experimentally determined values are presented in Table 3. They fall within the 0.02 to 0.58 range associated with parallel matrix flow that were determined in studies conducted on APC-2 [3,11]. However, the constants reported in [3,11] were obtained from consolidation experiments that involved much lower shear rates and matrix pressure gradients. The majority of the reported Kozeny constants were obtained from compression molded unidirectional APC-2 laminates that were consolidated at comparatively lower pressures and longer times.

A relatively simple method for predicting void content is to relate the dimensional changes each composite ring undergoes during the on-line consolidation process with its measured void content [2]. The relationship between the experimentally determined void content, V_v , and the percent reduction in towpreg thickness, $t_{\text{reduction}}$, is

$$V_v = 18.8 - 0.317 t_{\text{reduction}} \quad (\text{vol.}\%) \quad (9)$$

Equation 9 has an R² of 0.978. Again, the elimination of voids proceeds in a linear fashion as discussed above.

4.2 Deformation Model Predictions The deformation model was used to predict the applied load required to achieve the reported final fiber volume content for each of the five experiments conducted in the experimental investigation. The winding speed used in each experiment and the average measured fiber volume fraction of the three ring specimens from each experiment served as inputs to the model. The material constants employed in the deformation model simulation were for APC-2 (PEEK and AS4 carbon fibers) at a temperature of 400°C and are summarized in Table 2 [5].

Table 2: Material Constants for APC-2 AS4 12K Towpreg

Material Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Fiber radius	r_f	4	μm
Zero-shear rate matrix viscosity	η_0	280	$\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$
Time constant at which shear-thinning effects become important	λ	0.04	s
Viscosity model exponent	n	0.8	
Fiber spring constant	C	159	Pa
Highest fiber volume fraction obtainable	V_∞	0.829	

Figure 2 shows the predicted matrix pressure distribution generated within the nip for each experiment. All five show an expected steady pressure rise due to the backflow of matrix material out the nip entrance that occurs as the towpreg is compacted. The matrix pressure levels off towards the exit of the nip where the maximum fiber volume content (and subsequent maximum deformation) of the towpreg is achieved. Figure 3 shows the predicted fiber bed pressure distribution generated within the nip for each experiment. All five show an increase in the fiber bed pressure with increasing position in the nip. This trend was expected as Equation 6 indicates that the fiber bed pressure should increase with increasing fiber volume content. The fiber volume content of the towpreg increases with position in the nip due to the increase in the total amount of towpreg deformation. In addition, Figure 3 shows that the maximum fiber bed pressure occurs at the end of the nip where the maximum fiber volume content is achieved. The variation in the maximum (final) fiber volume content among the five experimental sets is reflected in the relative location of the peaks of each profile.

The predicted applied load required to achieve the final fiber volume content in each experiment was obtained by integrating both the matrix and fiber bed pressure distributions over the length of the nip and multiplying this by the width of the towpreg. Figure 4 provides shows the relationships between the predicted applied load and the fiber volume content for each of the three winding speeds studied in the experimental investigation. The figure shows an increase in the required applied load with increasing fiber volume content for a constant winding speed. This is because more load must be applied to the towpreg in order to achieve the increased deformation corresponding to the higher fiber volume content. Figure 4 also shows a decrease in the required applied load with increasing winding speed for a constant fiber volume content. This is due to the shear-thinning behavior of the molten matrix. The increase in shear rate with winding speed results in a decrease in the matrix viscosity. The lower viscosity reduces the resistance to matrix flow and thus reduces the load required to compact the towpreg to the given fiber volume fraction. In addition, the applied load appears to approach a minimum value as the fiber volume content is decreased for each of the winding speed profiles. One explanation for this is that there is a minimum load that must be applied to the compaction roller in order to maintain contact with the towpreg, no matter what winding speed is used.

4.3 Experimental Results The experimental results are summarized in Table 3. It should be noted that the values listed for each experiment represent an average of the three ring specimens fabricated in each experiment.

Table 3: Experimental Results Used in Statistical Analysis

Experiment (i=1,2,3)	Design Factors			Thickness Reduction (%)	Fiber Content (% by vol.)	Void Content (% by vol.)	Kozeny Constant
	Wind. Speed	Appl. Load	Speed/Load Interaction				
RS1-i	-	-	+	38.6	55.6	6.8	0.150
RS2-i	-	+	-	40.8	56.0	5.6	0.417
RS3-i	+	+	+	49.3	60.5	3.3	0.051
RS4-i	+	-	-	45.8	58.5	4.3	0.022
RS5-i	n/a	n/a	n/a	45.8	58.9	4.2	0.068

Statistical analyses were performed on the data to determine the levels at which the effects of the process parameters were significant and to obtain numerical estimates of the effects. The results of the ANOVA are summarized in *Table 4*.

Table 4: ANOVA Results

Source of Variation	Significance Level (%)		
	Thickness Reduction	Fiber Volume Content	Void Content
Winding Speed	99.9	99.1	99.9
Applied Load	99.8	70.6	94.3
Speed/Load	72.5	54.2	17.3

Values with a level of 95% or greater signify confidence that there is a statistically meaningful relationship between the source and the property.

4.4 Comparison of Theoretical and Experimental Results *Figure 4* provides a graphical representation of the correlation between the theoretical (predicted) applied load and the actual (measured) applied load. Both the theoretical predictions and the experimental results followed the same general trend: the required applied load increases with increasing fiber volume content and decreases with increasing winding speed. The average deviation in the applied load predictions was 23 percent, which is quite good considering the simplifying assumptions made. These results show the viscoelastic response of the system, facilitating the use of higher speeds due to the shear thinning behavior of the composite.

Although the lowest void content obtained with the single-roller, on-line consolidation mechanism in the experimental investigation was not within the range of void contents desired by industry (1-2%), it is believed that the pre-existing voids within the towpreg limited the minimum void content that could be achieved in the final, consolidated part. This is because the pre-existing voids were generally located in fiber-rich regions where there was insufficient matrix to mobilize and remove all the voids and to fill in spatial gaps.

While it is difficult to quantify the optimum processing conditions for filament winding APC-2 towpreg based on the experimental and theoretical results, the results indicate that increasing either the applied load, the winding speed, or both will increase the degree of consolidation and overall quality of the finished part for the range of winding speed and applied load studied. In addition, the recommended processing temperature of 400°C for APC-2 proved adequate for achieving consolidation on-line during the filament winding process. The temperature was high enough above the melting point of PEEK to reduce sufficiently the matrix viscosity and was low enough to prevent degradation of the PEEK matrix.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A one-dimensional, semi-empirical, on-line consolidation process model that describes the deformation and flow phenomena that occur during the filament winding of thermoplastic composite towpregs using a single-roller, on-line consolidation mechanism was proposed. The deformation model was used to predict the applied load necessary to achieve a desired fiber volume content of rings consisting of 6 mm wide APC-2 AS4 12K towpreg consolidated at 400°C and at various winding speeds. The winding speed was found to significantly (at 99% confidence level) affect all three of the dependent parameters. The applied load was found to significantly affect (at a 99% confidence level) the thickness and (at a 94% confidence level) void content of the ring specimens. The results of the consolidation testing compared well to the consolidation model's predictions. Both the theoretical predictions and the experimental results followed the same general trend: the required applied load increases with increasing fiber volume content and decreases with increasing winding speed due to shear thinning effects.

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Figure 1: Lay-up Scheme Used for Pressure/Flow Analysis of Nip Region

Figure 2: Matrix Pressure Distribution Within Nip for Experiments RS1 - RS5

Figure 3: Fiber Bed Pressure Distribution Within Nip for Experiments RS1 - RS5

Figure 4: Comparison of Predicted and Measured Relationships Between Applied Load and Fiber Volume Content